

Reconstructable Uterus-Derived Materials for Uterus Recovery toward Efficient Live Births

Artical summary

Production of Reconstructable ECM and RUM

The production of RUM (reconstructable uterine models) involved culturing mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) in a reconstructable ECM. MSCs were isolated from placental villi according to previous protocols. These cells were then placed in a reconstructable ECM to create RUM injectable gel and RUM patches. The production of these structures was controlled by adjusting MSC density and ECM concentration in the PBS medium. The RUM injectable gel was obtained with a concentration of 2.3 mg/ml ECM and MSC density of 1×10^6 , while the RUM patch had a concentration of 4.5 mg/ml ECM and a density of 2×10^6 MSCs. Microscopic observations showed that MSCs adhered well to the ECM, spread out, and proliferated, with a significant increase in cell numbers over the week of culture. Microscopic analysis and staining indicated high cell viability and good cell structure. Both the RUM gel and patch demonstrated excellent adhesive properties to the endometrium and uterine wall, suggesting their potential for uterine treatment and regeneration.

Live Births After Various Interventions

Fertility is considered a key indicator for assessing uterine function regeneration. The study was conducted on Sprague-Dawley (SD) rats with severe uterine damage. Assessments included the implantation of fertilized eggs, pregnancy, embryonic development, and the number of live births. Fifteen days post-surgery, the rats were mated, and pregnancy was monitored by observing the appearance of vaginal plugs and performing palpation. Euthanasia was performed between days 21 and 23 post-mating. Reproductive outcomes were evaluated, including the ability of the endometrium to accept embryos (pregnancy rate, mean time to successful pregnancy, average number of fetuses), and the ability of uterine horns to support embryonic development and live births.

The study of the synergistic treatment mechanism using the RUM injectable gel and RUM patches focused on three key aspects aimed at supporting uterine regeneration and improving live birth outcomes.

First, the natural properties of RUM supporting embryo implantation were analyzed. It was found that ECM (extracellular matrix) derived from the uterus contains high levels of progesterone (P) and progesterone receptors (PR), both essential for successful embryo implantation. Mass spectrometry analyses showed that both P and PR play crucial roles in the

biological process, enhancing cellular components and regulating smooth muscle cell migration. These protein-protein interactions positively influenced supporting live births. We compared the survival, efficacy, and retention ability of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) in RUM (in vivo magnetic resonance). MSCs were labeled with green fluorescent protein (GFP) and luciferase via lentivirus transfection, allowing real-time monitoring in living organisms.

Conclusions

We demonstrated that RUM (reorganized uterine models) can be adapted to different states and shapes, achieving nearly complete uterine regeneration, leading to high success in live births in rats with severe uterine damage. Compared to traditional biomaterial scaffold-based uterine regeneration systems, RUM offers several significant advantages:

1. RUM can be transformed into injectable gels and patches, allowing customization of the uterine structure.
2. RUM effectively prevents intrauterine adhesions, supports endometrial regeneration, and accelerates wound healing. Unlike systems based on massive biomaterial scaffolds, our injectable gel deeply penetrates the endometrial cavity, preventing adhesions and promoting regeneration and collagen muscle reconstruction. The RUM patch, applied to the uterine wall, prevents adhesion between the wound and abdominal tissue and accelerates wound healing.
3. RUM demonstrates high efficacy in achieving live births in rats with uterine damage. The injectable gel and synergistic patch system provide normal pregnancy progression in the regenerated uterus, supporting fetal development and live births.

Authors

Xiao Yi:

Xiao Yi is a Chinese scientist associated with research in the field of regenerative medicine. Chinese Academy of Sciences Fujian Inst Res Struct Matter FUZHOU, FUJIAN, PEOPLES R CHINA

Research Centre for Artificial Organ and Tissue Engineering & Institute of Regenerative Medicine Department of Hepatobiliary Surgery II Zhujiang Hospital Cancer Research Institute School of Basic Medical Sciences Southern Medical University Guangzhou, Guangdong Province 510280, P. R. China

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Prof. Dr. Fan Liu:

Prof. Dr. Fan Liu is an outstanding research scientist in the field of structural interactomics and proteomics.

Prof. Dr. Liu graduated from Fudan University in Shanghai with a B.Sc. in Biology. Afterwards she joined the lab of Prof. Dr. Mike Goshe at North Carolina State University and obtained her PhD in Biochemistry in 2013. Liu did her postdoc in the lab of Prof. Dr. Albert Heck (Utrecht, The Netherlands).

In 2017 Liu joined the Leibniz-Forschungsinstitut for Molecular Pharmacology (FMP) in Berlin as a group leader for Structural Interactomics and head of the proteomics research platform. In 2020, Liu is jointly appointed as W2-S professor with the Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin.

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Kunjie Gao:

Department of Gynecology, Zhujiang Hospital, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou, Guangdong Province, P. R. China

Feng Chen:

Department of Gynecology, Zhujiang Hospital, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou, Guangdong Province, P. R. China

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Yifeng Wang:

Yifeng Wang is a research scientist in the field of organic chemistry, focusing mainly on radical and organobor chemistry.

Artificial Organ and Tissue Engineering Research Center and Institute of Regenerative Medicine, Department of Hepatobiliary Surgery II, Zhujiang Hospital, Cancer Research Institute, School of Basic Medical Sciences, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou, Guangdong Province, 510280 PR China

Department of Gynecology, Zhujiang Hospital, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou, Guangdong Province, P.R. China

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Huang Yi:

Beijing Institute of Technology, Chinese Academy of Sciences University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, CAS, University of Liverpool R&D Ctr Huawei Technol Sweden AB

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Yi Gao:

Research Centre for Artificial Organ and Tissue Engineering & Institute of Regenerative Medicine, Department of Hepatobiliary Surgery II, Zhujiang Hospital, Cancer Research Institute, School of Basic Medical Sciences, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou, Guangdong Province, 510280 P. R. China

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dr Xuefeng Wang:

Department of Gynecology, Zhujiang Hospital, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou, Guangdong Province, P. R. China

Shutao Wang:

CAS Key Laboratory of Bio-inspired Materials and Interfacial Science, CAS Center for Excellence in Nanoscience, Technical Institute of Physics and Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100190, P R China

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Jun-Bing Fan:

Artificial Organ and Tissue Engineering Research Center and Institute of Regenerative Medicine, Department of Hepatobiliary Surgery II, Zhujiang Hospital, Cancer Research Institute, School of Basic Medical Sciences, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou, Guangdong Province, 510280 PR China

Weijie Zhou:

Department of Pathology, School of Basic Medical Sciences, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou 510515, P R China

Huayan Li:

Department of Gynecology Zhujiang Hospital Southern Medical University Guangzhou, Guangdong Province, P. R. China

Huijiao Fu:

Department of Gynecology The Third Affiliated Hospital of Southern Medical University Guangzhou, Guangdong, P. R. Chin

Yi Gao:

Guangzhou Medical University, Hainan Medical University, Southern Medical University - China, University of Hong Kong
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